

In-Service Training On Job Performances of Business Teachers in Secondary Schools in Ikere Local Government Area, Ekiti State

AUTHOR(S): OGUNLEYE Funmilola Mary, ENIJUNI
Anthony Tola (PhD),

Abstract

The study was on in-service training on job performance of business teachers in Secondary schools in Ikere Local Government area in Ekiti state. Four research questions were raised and one hypothesis was formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The study adopted survey research design. The population of the study comprised 70 business subject teachers in all the Secondary School in the area of study. All the business teachers were used since the population was manageable. The instrument used was a questionnaire titled in-service training on job performance of business teachers in Secondary Schools Questionnaire (ITJPBSQ). The instrument was given to experts in Business Education for content and face validity. The internal consistency of the instrument was ascertained using Cronbach alpha with a Coefficient value of 0.74. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to answer all the research questions. The null hypothesis was tested using t-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that coaching, mentoring, job rotation and job shadowing influence business teachers' job performance with high extent. It was therefore recommended that School authorities should adopt mentoring strategies that can expose teachers to necessary work ethics and rudiments that could enhance their job performance, Schools authorities should promote job rotation programmes in order to update and complement business teachers' knowledge, skills and competencies, among others.

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About Author

Author(s):

OGUNLEYE Funmilola Mary

Business Education Department
Bamidele Olumilua University of Education, Science and
Technology,
Ikere-Ekiti, Ekiti State.
ogunleyefunmilolamary@gmail.com.

ENIJUNI Anthony Tola (PhD)

Business Education Department
Bamidele Olumilua University of Education, Science and
Technology,
Ikere-Ekiti, Ekiti State
enijuni.anthony@bouestic.edu.ng

Introduction

Quality education is the degree to which education is said to be of high standard, satisfies basic learning needs and enriches the lives of learners and their overall experience of living (Kennedy, 2015). The achievement of quality education rests squarely on the shoulders of teachers who need appropriate motivation and training to produce the desired educational productivity. Given the fact that education is one of the important factors that help in bringing about rapid social and economic development in any given nation, the role of teachers cannot be downplayed.

Teachers play significant, critical and valued roles in the educational system. The teacher is at the center of all educational enterprises. The teacher aids the interpretation, implementation of the curriculum to the benefit of the student, school and nation at large. In order to meet the demands of the curriculum, policies, school goals and education objectives, teachers have to play multiple roles, which may include student discipline, classroom management, guidance and counseling, forming of lesson notes, grading of students, record of students' progress, update parents on the progress of their children, supervising and organizing school functions, extra and intra-curricular activities and so on. Due to the multiple task of teachers everyone employed to take up the role has to be morally sound, emotionally intelligent, content smart, qualified and have passion for the profession. Therefore, teachers have to be constantly equipped to meet up to the standard expected from them by the students, parents, school and nation, in an evolving world, where things are bound to change, these teachers also have to evolve in their methodology and manner of approach to various situations in and outside the classroom, the key way to ensure that these teachers are evolving is by constantly and periodically training them.

Business teachers are teachers who teach business related subjects in secondary schools. These include: Business studies, Office practice, Financial Accounting, Marketing, Commerce, etc. they are primarily saddled with the responsibility of implementing business subjects curriculum. They equip students with the requisite skills, knowledge, competencies and attitudes necessary for job creation and to become profitably engaged in order to be able to contribute expressively to the economic growth of the nation. Business teachers contribute to national economic growth and development in the educational industry particularly in secondary schools.

Job performance is how well an individual performs their tasks and responsibilities in a workplace. It encompasses various aspects, including the quality and quantity of work produced, the ability to meet deadlines, the level of collaboration with colleagues, adherence to organization policies and overall contributions to its goals and objectives. It is the sum total of an employee execution of an assigned tasks (Adeola, Waliu, Adewale and Opeyemi & Olowoporoku 2017). Job performances is typically evaluated by supervisors or managers through performances reviews, feedbacks and metrics to assess. The component that constitute business teachers job performance in secondary schools include; prepare and deliver instruction, lesson note preparation, students' evaluation, room management, counseling students, maintaining students' attendance record, etc. in order to carry out these tasks successfully, business teacher must undergo constant in-service training such as coaching, mentoring, job rotation and job shadowing.

Coaching is a form of development in which an experienced person called a coach supports a learner or clients in achieving a specific personal or professional goal by providing training and guidance. The learner is sometimes called a coachee. Coaching involves supportive and

collaborative relationship in which the coach uses various techniques, questioning and feedback to guide the coachee in identifying and working towards their objectives (Haslinda Abdullah, 2019). Coaching can be applied in various fields including personal development, career, leadership, sports and more to enhance performance, problem solving and self awareness. It is a valuable tool for individual to make positive changes and achieve their potential. Coaching can play a vital role in enhancing job performances by focusing on skill development, goal setting, feedback ,motivation ,problem solving ,stress management ,leadership development and accountability. It provides individual with the guidance and support they need to excel in their roles and contribute positively to their organizations

Mentoring is a process in which an experienced individual known as a mentor provides guidance, support and knowledge to someone less experienced known as mentee, to help them develop personally or professionally. Coaching is how individuals are helped to perform better to achieve the goals and objectives of an organization (Mullins, 2015) Mentoring can have a significant impact on job performances in various ways, mentoring can help young business teacher to acquire new skills or enhance existing ones through the guidance of the experienced business teacher. This may directly improve job performance of business teacher.

Job rotation on the other hand is a Human Resources management strategy in which employees are periodically moved or toted through different positions or tasks within an organization (Parker, 2012). The primary purpose of job rotation is to provide employees with exposure to variety of roles and responsibilities rather than keeping them fixed in a single job. Job rotation can be structured in various ways such as moving employees through different departments, job families or geographical locations. It is important to carefully plan and communicate job rotations to ensure that they align with no the individual and organizational goals and do not disrupt essential operations. When implemented effectively, job rotation can be a valuable tool for employee job performance and organizational growth. Job rotation have a significant influence on job performance both in positive and potentially challenging way by enhancing skills, investing engagement, provide learning opportunities and fostering adaptability. However, it should be implemented thoughtfully to manage potential challenges and ensure that the overall impact is beneficial to both employees and organization.

Job shadowing is a professional development and learning activity where an individual, typically a student or someone interested in a particular career spends time observing and closely following a professional in their workplace (Nwaeke & Onyebuchi, 2017). During the shadowing experience, the person gains insight into the daily responsibilities, tasks and work environment. The primary purpose is you observe and learn how to perform tasks or take on responsibilities. It allows the shadowing individual to see firsthand what a particular job or profession entails. Job shadowing is an effective way for individuals to explore carted, gain real- world insights and make informed decision about their future career paths. Job performances can positively be influenced by job shadowing by providing valuable insights, skills and confidence. It helps individual adapt to work environment, understand company's culture and build relationships that can support the growth and success in their chosen career paths.

Statement of the Problem

It has also been seen that lack of professionalism has crept into the fabric of the school work force across primary, secondary and tertiary institutions, which has been traced to so many root factors. The dysfunctional nature of teacher's orientation, employment and posting has further developed a crack in the wall of teacher quality. This has further to poor academic performance, undesirable learning experience, absenteeism, lateness to school and social vices. The long term implication will include bad quality of graduates produced,

increase in indiscipline, increase in crime rate, destruction of government and private property, non-attainment of the goals and objectives of the education system and so on. It is on this basis the researcher intends to investigate the influence of in-service training on business teacher's job performances in Secondary Schools in Ikere Local Government Area, Ekiti State.

This study examined the influence of in-service training on job performances of business teachers in secondary schools in Ikere Local Government Area, Ekiti State. This study will specifically seek to determine:

1. the extent in which coaching influences job performances of business teachers In secondary schools in Ikere Local Government, Ekiti State;
2. the extent in which mentoring influences job performances of business teachers in secondary schools in Ikere Local Government Area, Ekiti State;
3. the extent in which job rotation influences job performances of business teachers in Secondary Schools in Ikere Local Government Area, Ekiti State; and
4. the extent in which job shadowing influences job performances of business teachers in secondary schools in Ikere Local Government Area, Ekiti State.

Research Question

The following research questions guided the study

1. To what extent will coaching influences the job performances of business teachers in secondary schools in Ikere Local Government Area, Ekiti State?
2. To what extent will mentoring influences the job performances of business teachers in secondary schools in Ikere Local Government Area, Ekiti State?
3. To what extent will job rotation influences job performances of business teachers in secondary schools in Ikere Local Government Area, Ekiti State?
4. To what extent will job shadowing influences the job performances of business teachers in secondary schools in Ikere Local Government Area, Ekiti State?

Research Hypothesis

Ho1: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female business teachers in response to extent in which coaching influences the job performances of business teachers in secondary schools in Ikere Local Government Area, Ekiti State

Methodology

The study adopted survey research design. The population of the study comprised 70 business teachers from all public Secondary Schools in Ikere-Ekiti Local Government Area. The entire population was used for the study since it was manageable. A structured questionnaire that was divided into two parts was used for data collection. Part A was on personal data of respondents while part B contained a total of 25 opinion statements designed in a 4-points rating scale ranging from Very High Extent (VHE) – 1; High Extent

(HE)- 3; Low Extent (LE) – 2; and Very Low Extent (VLE). The entire questionnaire were correctly filled and returned. The instrument was validated by three experts from the department of business education, Bamidele Olumilua University of Education Science and Technology, Ikere-Ekiti, Ekiti-State. The Cronbach Alpha was used in ascertaining the reliability of the instrument after administering the instrument to 15 business teachers in two Secondary Schools at Emure-Ekiti. The in-service training on job performances of business teachers scale reported a Cronbach Alpha coefficient value of 0.74 which showed that all the items in the scale measured were all reliable.

The data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, Mean and Standard Deviation (SD) were used to answer the research questions, while t-test statistics was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. A mean of 2.50 was used for decision such that only item equal or greater than 2.50 was regarded as high extent, while a mean of less than 2.50 was regarded as Low extent. For the hypothesis, decision rule was based on the probability value and 0.05 alpha level of significance, the null hypothesis was accepted when the probability value is greater than 0.05, and rejected when the probability value is less than 0.05.

Results

Research Question One: To what extent will coaching influences the job performances of business teachers in secondary schools in Ikere Local Government Area, Ekiti State?

Table 1: Mean Rating and standard Deviation of Respondents' Opinion on the extent to which coaching influence job performance of business teachers.

S/N	Items	X	SD	Remarks
1	Coaching training that I received boosted my job	2.82	2.59	High extent
2	Through coaching my research skills, ability and knowledge has been enhanced	3.20	2.55	High extent
3	Coaching provide me and other mentee valuable information and enlightened the school through my performance	3.01	2.17	High extent
4	Coaching help me to impact knowledge as a result of skill acquired for job performance	2.67	2.83	High Extent
5	Coaching allowed me to contribute ideals on how my work will make progress for job performance	3.20	2.72	High extent
	Grand mean	2.98		High extent

The result in Table 1 reveals that the grand mean is 3.02. This outcome indicated high extent of influence of coaching on job performance of business teachers in Secondary Schools in Ikere Local Government. All the items mean were above the decision rule mean of 2.50 which signifies high extent.

Research Question Two: To what extent will mentoring influences the job performances of business teachers in secondary schools in Ikere Local Government Area, Ekiti State?

Table 2: Mean Rating and standard Deviation of Respondents' Opinion on the extent to which mentoring influence job performance of business teachers.

S/N	Items Statement	X	SD	Remarks
1.	Mentoring improved your productivity and job performance	3.48	3.11	High extent
2.	Your suggestion is valid as a result of mentoring for job performance	3.31	2.70	High extent
3.	My school used mentoring to help acquire skills to do job	2.97	3.50	High extent
4.	Mentoring broaden my insight in my work/classroom performance	3.18	2.76	High extent
5.	Mentoring enable me take charge in teaching, learning and carrying out my job performance	3.20	2.92	High extent
	Grand mean	3.23	2.92	High extent

The result in Table 2 reveals that the grand mean is 3.20. This outcome indicated high extent of influence of mentoring on job performance of business teachers in Secondary Schools in Ikere Local Government. All the items mean were above the decision rule mean of 2.50 which signifies high extent.

Research Question Three: To what extent will job rotation influences the job performances of business teachers in secondary schools in Ikere Local Government Area, Ekiti State?

Table 3: Mean Rating and standard Deviation of Respondents' Opinion on the extent to which job rotation influence job performance of business teachers.

S/N	Items Statement	X	SD	Remarks
1	Job rotation promote effectiveness of business teachers in the school for performance	3.16	2.75	High extent
2	Job rotation help to promote communication between me and management for performance	3.11	2.71	High extent
3	Job rotation help me to perform different assignment in my work	3.37	2.52	High extent
4	Accumulated experience through job rotation increased my job performance	2.77	2.24	High extent
5	Job rotation helps employees to move from one department to another for job performance	3.45	2.53	High extent
6	Job rotation enhance employees performance for career development	3.25	2.85	High extent
7	Job rotation helps me to achieve effective result performance in any school	3.40	2.60	High extent
	Grand Mean	3.21		High extent

The result in Table 3 reveals that the grand mean is 3.07 This outcome indicated high extent of influence of job rotation on job performance of business teachers in Secondary Schools in Ikere Local Government. All the items mean were above the decision rule mean of 2.50 which signifies high extent.

Research Question Four: To what extent will Job shadowing influences the job performances of business teachers in secondary schools in Ikere Local Government Area, Ekiti State?

Table 4: Mean Rating and standard Deviation of Respondents' Opinion on the extent to which job shadowing influence job performance of business teachers.

S/N	Items Statement	X	SD	Remarks
18	Through job shadowing my training has given me insight on classroom management and performance	2.91	2.93	High extent
19	Your experience through job shadowing has supported you to accomplishment of career path	3.18	2.85	High extent
20	Job shadowing has effectively help me work with new staff to improve my performance	3.15	3.15	High extent
21	Job shadowing enhances my participation to perform tasks	3.12	2.85	High extent
22	Job shadowing help you in developing your knowledge, skills and experience for your job	3.27	2.57	High extent
23	Job shadowing help you to improve your communication across department for your job performance in your school	3.38	2.55	High extent
24	Job shadowing help to share your experiences with colleagues in different departments about your performance	3.21	2.97	High extent
25	Through job shadowing, I got proper mastery to excel in job performance	3.44	2.72	High extent
	Grand Mean	3.20		High extent

The result in Table 4 reveals that the grand mean is 3.20. This outcome indicated high extent of influence of job shadowing on job performance of business teachers in Secondary Schools in Ikere Local Government. All the items mean were above the decision rule mean of 2.50 which signifies high extent.

Research Hypothesis

H01: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of male and female business teachers in response to extent in which coaching influences the job performances of business teachers in secondary schools in Ikere Local Government Area, Ekiti State?

Table 5: T-test analysis of Mean Rating of of male and female business teachers in response to extent in which coaching influences the job performances of business teachers

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-cal	p-value	Remarks
Male	38	3.32	0.58	68	0.14	0.78	NS
Female	32	3.54	0.65				

The result of data analysis in Table 5 revealed t-value of 0.14 and a probability value of 0.78. Since the probability value of 0.78 is greater than significance value of 0.05 at which its being tested. Therefore, the null hypothesis is hereby accepted and this means that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of male and female business teachers in response to extent in which coaching influences their job performances.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from research question one in table 1 revealed that coaching influence job performance of business teachers in secondary School in Ikere Local Government as respondents indicated high extent. The findings of this study is in agreement with the findings of Cordingles & Bell (2017) who affirmed that coaching continuously update teachers' knowledge, skills and interest in their chosen profession. This will in turn enhance their job performance. The findings from research question two in table 2 revealed that mentoring influence job performance of business teachers in secondary School in Ikere Local Government as respondents indicated high extent. The findings is in consonance with Sonjo, Despina, Biljana and Jadranka (2018) who asserted that mentoring assist teachers in developing talents and enable them to meet their expected performance.

The findings from research question three in table 3 revealed that job rotation influence job performance of business teachers in secondary School in Ikere Local Government as respondents indicated high extent. The findings collaborates the findings of Walu (2019) who stated that accumulated experience through job rotation increased job performance of employee. The findings from research question four in table 4 revealed that job shadowing influence job performance of business teachers in secondary School in Ikere Local Government as respondents indicated high extent. The findings collaborates the findings of Makoveel (2021) who stated that accumulated experience through job rotation increased job performance of employee. The finding is in harmony with the findings of Nwaeke & Onyebuchi (2017).who affirmed that job shadowing enables employee to know the scope, expectation and depth of their job.

The result of the hypothesis in table 5 reveals that there is no significance difference between the mean rating of male and female business teachers in their response to extent in which coaching influences the job performances of business teachers in secondary schools in Ikere Local Government Area, Ekiti- State. Hence, the null hypothesis was retained since the probability value of 0.78 is greater than 0.05 level of significance. This implies that, the extent in which coaching influences job performance of male business teachers is the same as that of the female business teachers.

Conclusion

The study indicates that coaching, mentoring, job rotation and job shadowing are part of in-service training. The study further revealed that coaching, mentoring, job rotation and job shadowing activities have high extent influence on job performance of business teachers in Secondary Schools in Ikere-Local Government Area, Ekiti-State.

Recommendation

Consequent upon findings, the study recommends the following;

1. There should be coaching programme for business teachers in order to ensure improvement in their job performance.
2. School authorities should adopt mentoring strategies that can expose teachers to necessary work ethics and rudiments that could enhance their job performance
3. Schools authorities should promote job rotation programmes in order to update and complement business teachers' knowledge, skills and competencies. This will improve their teaching quality
4. Job shadowing should be encouraged between experienced and young business teachers for them to share experience, expertise, knowledge and skills which will increase their job performance.

5. Coaching programme should be designed to accommodate all business teachers across gender in secondary school in order to improve their job performance.

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